

About Vacationment

vacationment is a technology company in the field of tourism that provides access for people to find and book a variety of transportation, accommodation, activities and lifestyle services, as well as finance. We have been established since November 2021 and based in Jakarta, Indonesia.

Tourism is a field that is very popular with the community, this is because traveling to a place can give someone a new experience that cannot be forgotten.

Often we have difficulty in making hotel reservations or booking transportation to travel to a place. Especially if we want to travel abroad which requires a tour guide.

We see this problem as a challenge for us to solve. Therefore Vacationment is here to assist you in achieving unforgettable travel moments.

If you want to contact us, please contact us via:

- Email : vacationment@gmail.com
- Instagram : [vacationment](#)
- Phone : +62 89529705058

Kind regards,

Vacationment Team